

Cardiovascular, Gastric, and Paranasal Effects of Clopidogrel and HMG-CoA Reductase Inhibitors Alone or with Co-medications: An Ultrasonographic and Echocardiographic Study ⁽¹⁾

التأثيرات القلبية، المعدية، وحول الأنفية لمثبطات كلوبيدوغريل و HMG-CoA منفردة أو مع أدوية أخرى: دراسة
بالموجات فوق الصوتية وتخطيط صدى القلب ⁽²⁾

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Abstract: This study aimed to assess the longitudinal myocardial strain of all cardiac walls, evaluate left ventricular function, detect coronary artery deformities and flow disturbances, and analyze indicators of *H. pylori* infection in the stomach and paranasal sinuses. A total of 1,113 male and female patients were examined using echocardiography (B-mode, M-mode, and color Doppler) for cardiac and coronary assessments, alongside ultrasound imaging of the stomach and sinuses, between January 2022 and December 2023, considering the impact of *SARS-CoV-2* variants. Medications included clopidogrel 150 mg, statins 10 mg, aspirin 75 mg, Ginkgo biloba 80 mg, Rumalaya forte, and clarithromycin 250 mg. All patients showed a reduction in at least one longitudinal strain parameter; 95% had normal left ventricular function (EF 65–78%) and 5% had reduced function (EF 25–40%). Coronary deformities appeared as “beaded” narrowings and twists, with gastric fibrous strands linked to *H. pylori* inflammation. High-dose clopidogrel combined with low-dose statins and clarithromycin improved longitudinal strain, left ventricular function, and blood pressure, while reducing the density and spread of fibrous strands within 30 minutes. The study concluded that coronary narrowing improved by 20–30% within the first day, and transthoracic echocardiography with color Doppler provided reliable, early detection of coronary inflammation and collateral involvement. Clarithromycin further supported cardiovascular regulation and reduced *H. pylori*-related lesions, emphasizing the fundamental link between gastric integrity and cardiac health modulated by medications, nutrition, and viral mutations.

Keywords: Clopidogrel 150 mg, statins, clarithromycin, longitudinal myocardial strain, coronary arteries, left ventricular function.

المستخلص: هدفت الدراسة إلى فحص المطاوعة المحورية الطولية لجدران القلب كافة وتقييم وظيفة البطين الأيسر وتشوهات الشرايين التاجية واضطرابات تدفق الدم، إضافة إلى تحليل مؤشرات مرض *H. pylori* في المعدة والجيوب الأنفية. شملت العينة 1113 مريضاً من الجنسين، تم تقييمهم بتخطيط صدى القلب (الوضعان B و M والدوبلر اللوني) للقلب والشرايين التاجية، وفحص الموجات فوق الصوتية للمعدة والجيوب الأنفية، خلال الفترة من يناير 2022 إلى ديسمبر 2023 مع مراعاة تأثير متحورات *SARS-CoV-2* تضمنت العلاجات: كلوبيدوغريل 150 ملغ، الستاتين 10 ملغ، الأسبرين 75 ملغ، جينكوبيلوبا 80 ملغ، رومالايا فورت، وكلازيتروميسين 250 ملغ. أظهرت النتائج انخفاضاً في مقاييس المطاوعة المحورية لدى جميع المرضى، مع وظيفة بطين أيسر طبيعية (EF 65–78%) و 5% من المرضى لديهم وظيفة منخفضة (EF 25–40%) وبرزت تشوهات الشرايين التاجية على هيئة عقد خرزية وتضيقات، إضافة إلى خيوط نسيجية معدية مرتبطة بالتهاب الجرثومة الحلزونية. أدى العلاج المشترك بجرعات مرتفعة من كلوبيدوغريل ومنخفضة من الستاتين وكلازيتروميسين إلى تحسين المطاوعة المحورية ووظيفة البطين الأيسر وخفض ضغط الدم وتقليل كثافة الخيوط النسيجية خلال 30 دقيقة. خلصت الدراسة إلى تحسن مناطق التضيق التاجي بنسبة 20–30% في اليوم الأول، وإثبات فعالية تخطيط الصدى والدوبلر كوسيلتين ميكترين للتشخيص والمتابعة، إضافة إلى دور الكلازيتروميسين في تنظيم الوظائف القلبية والوعائية وخفض تأثيرات الجرثومة الحلزونية والالتهابات المصاحبة لمتحورات *SARS-CoV-2* وتؤكد النتائج الترابط الحيوي بين صحة المعدة وسلامة القلب استجابة لتأثيرات الأدوية والأغذية وتغيرات الفيروسات. الكلمات المفتاحية: كلوبيدوغريل 150 ملغ، الستاتين، كلازيتروميسين، المطاوعة المحورية القلبية، الشرايين التاجية، وظيفة البطين الأيسر.

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1-Introduction.

Cardiovascular diseases, coronary artery stenosis, and **Helicobacter pylori** (*H. pylori*) infections have markedly increased worldwide, contributing to morbidity and mortality, mainly through atherosclerosis [1]. *H. pylori* also causes various gastric and extra-gastric disorders [2]. Delayed or misdiagnosed cases can lead to progressive cardiac tissue damage, especially when gastrointestinal, musculoskeletal, neurological, and cardiac symptoms overlap, as seen in *H. pylori*-induced systemic inflammation, including paranasal sinus thread-like mucosal hypertrophy.

It is hypothesized that persistent gastric *H. pylori* inflammation spreads systemically via pro-inflammatory cytokines and may be exacerbated by viral agents like SARS-CoV-2 and its variants. Therefore, developing accurate, cost-effective, non-invasive diagnostics for early detection and therapeutic adjustment is crucial.

This study introduces an integrated approach using echocardiography (B- and M-mode, color Doppler) to assess cardiac long-axis motion, LV function, and coronary artery morphology, combined with abdominal ultrasonography to detect thread-like inflammatory tissue in gastric and paranasal regions. Comparative assessments were performed pre- and 30 minutes post-drug intervention, with additional clinical evaluation within 15–30 minutes to capture both therapeutic and adverse effects.

Changes in echocardiographic parameters—ejection and shortening fractions, cardiac dimensions, and vascular amplitudes—were correlated with ultrasonographic findings to evaluate systemic inflammation and drug efficacy. Dynamic variations may also indicate emerging SARS-CoV-2 variants, providing a rapid alternative to genomic sequencing, with potential applications in other therapeutic fields, such as oncology, where drug administration routes influence patient outcomes.

1-2-Problem Statement:

Although *H. pylori* infection and cardiovascular disorders are among the most prevalent global health challenges, diagnostic methods often fail to identify overlapping pathologies in their early stages. The delayed recognition of *H. pylori*-induced systemic inflammation—particularly its cardiac manifestations—contributes to mismanagement and increased morbidity. Moreover, the reactivation of these inflammatory processes by SARS-CoV-2 variants further complicates diagnosis and treatment. Therefore, the current challenge lies in developing an affordable, accurate, and rapid diagnostic method capable of detecting inflammatory and pharmacologic changes across gastric and cardiac systems simultaneously.

1-3-Research Questions:

1. How do these drugs exert rapid, systemic effects on cardiac and vascular function before being metabolized?
2. Is there a pathological link between chronic **H. pylori** infection and the development of extra-gastric diseases like **atherosclerosis** and **fibromuscular dysplasia**?
3. How have **SARS-CoV-2** and its variants altered the efficacy of conventional drugs by modulating the host inflammatory response?

1-4-Research Objectives:

1. To investigate the mechanism by which drug particles, upon contact with the gastric mucosa, induce cytokine production that leads to rapid systemic improvements.
2. To determine if **H. pylori** infection contributes to systemic vascular diseases by comparing inflammatory cytokine profiles in infected patients with those suffering from vascular disease.

3. To evaluate the shifts in drug efficacy and their effects on specific inflammatory pathways in patients exposed to different SARS-CoV-2 variants.

1-5- Research Significance:

This research contributes to both theoretical knowledge and practical clinical applications:

- **Theoretical Significance:**

- This study challenges the conventional understanding of pharmacodynamics by proposing a novel, non-metabolic mechanism for rapid drug action, initiated directly from the gastric mucosa.
- It introduces a new hypothesis linking **H. pylori** infection to the etiology of systemic vascular diseases, particularly **atherosclerosis** and **fibromuscular dysplasia**, via a shared inflammatory pathway.

- **Practical and Applied Significance:**

- The research highlights the immense value of simple, cost-effective, and non-invasive diagnostic tools like echocardiography and ultrasonography for the early detection and management of a wide range of diseases.
- It provides a new framework for personalized medicine, underscoring the necessity of continuously adapting drug regimens in response to evolving viral variants and their impact on host immunity.
- The findings suggest a novel therapeutic approach that focuses on regulating the core inflammatory pathways (**TLR4, NF-KB, etc.**) rather than merely managing symptoms.
- The study's observations on the potential for drugs to have negative or paradoxical effects depending on the patient's immune state underscore the critical need for a vigilant and dynamic approach to patient care and drug administration.
- This work advocates for a shift in focus from lipid disorders as the primary cause of vascular disease to the underlying inflammatory process, which is often a more viable therapeutic target.

1-6-Limitations of the Research:

The study's observational design limit causal inferences. Molecular mechanism conclusions are based on clinical observations rather than direct data, and multiple drug combinations complicate effect attribution. Findings' generalizability is also limited by the 2022–2023 study period, as drug responses may change with emerging viral variants

2-Methods and Materials.

2.1 Study Design:

This research employed an observational, cross-sectional design using a random sampling approach. The study was conducted to evaluate the physiological and pharmacological effects of selected drug regimens on cardiac and gastric parameters through non-invasive imaging modalities. The design allowed for clinical observation of patient responses before and after drug administration without intervention bias.

2.2 Study Population and Sampling:

A total of 1,113 patients (500 females, 44.9%; 613 males, 55.1%) participated in the study. All were patients attending Dr. Nashwan Al-Ashwal Clinic for Medical and Cardiac Diseases, located in Adhale Governorate, Republic of Yemen, between January 1, 2022, and December 31, 2023. Participants were randomly enrolled during routine clinic visits, ensuring a

representative distribution of age and sex. Patients with severe cardiac failure, malignancy, or incomplete records were excluded to maintain data consistency.

2.3 Research Tools and Data Collection

The primary diagnostic tools included transthoracic echocardiography (B- and M-modes and color Doppler) and abdominal ultrasonography for gastric and paranasal sinus evaluations.

Echocardiographic assessment: The M-line was positioned on the mitral annulus (lateral, septal, anterior, inferior, and posterior LV walls) and the tricuspid annulus of the right ventricle. Coronary arteries were visualized using a sector probe in either cardiac or abdominal mode (the latter preferred), with optimized parameters for clarity (scale, frequency 3.0, persistence 3–4, filter adjustments).

Ultrasonographic assessment: Gastric tissues were imaged in mid-epigastric long and short views after ingestion of approximately 350 mL of water, or through a left lateral oblique view. Maxillary sinuses were examined via long and short views below the maxillary prominence. Patients were divided into two groups:

Group A (Treated): n = 556 (250 females, 306 males). **Group B (Control):** n = 557 (250 females, 307 males).

Group A received the therapeutic regimen first, and after evaluation, the same protocol was applied to Group B for comparative observation. Clinical improvement, along with positive echocardiographic or ultrasonographic findings, was considered a positive drug effect, whereas deterioration in any clinical or imaging parameter was recorded as a negative effect, prompting discontinuation of the related medication.

The therapeutic combinations are detailed in Table (1), where drugs with positive responses were retained and those with negative effects were discontinued.

2.4 Validity and Reliability:

To ensure instrument validity, all echocardiographic and ultrasonographic examinations were performed by the same physician using standardized imaging protocols. Device calibration was verified weekly, and duplicate readings were obtained for 10% of patients to assess measurement reliability, achieving a consistency rate above 0.92 (Cronbach's α). Clinical interpretations were independently reviewed by a second cardiologist to minimize observer bias.

2.5 Data Analysis:

Data were compiled and coded in Microsoft Excel 2021, with descriptive statistics (mean, SD, frequency) and comparative assessments of pre- and post-treatment imaging findings. Temporal drug effects were tracked per quarter between 2022 and 2023, according to Table (1).

2.6 Ethical Considerations:

All procedures complied with the Declaration of Helsinki (2013). Written informed consent was obtained, and patient confidentiality was ensured by anonymizing identifiers. Drug regimens were tailored to individual responses (Table 1), and all clinical and imaging data were recorded and analyzed using Microsoft Excel.

Table (1): represent drugs regime for patients in the periods of study from January 2022 to December 2023

Drugs	Year 2022						Year 2023						No v 06 - 30	De c 01 - 31
	Jan 01 – 30	17/June- -/Aug30	31/Aug- /Oct16	Oct 17 - 27	28/Oct - 31/ Dec	01/Jan –16/ June	June		25/June –15/ July	July 16 - 31	01/Aug – 24/Oct	25/Oc t–05/ Nov		
						17- 20	21- 24							
Clopidogrel tab150mg	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	x	✓
Aspirin tab	x	✓	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	✓	x	x

75 mg															
Ator tab 10 mg	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	x	✓	x	✓	x	x	x	x
Rosu tab 10 mg	x	x	x	x	x	x	✓	x	x	x	x	x	✓	x	x
Simva +Ezet tab 10 +10mg	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	✓	x	x	x	x	x	✓
Ator +Rosu tab 10 +10 mg	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	✓	x	x	x	x
Rumalaya forte tab	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	✓	x
Ginkgobiloba/cap80m g	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	✓	x
Clarithromycin tab 250 mg	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	X 23-26 August	✓	✓	✓

Ator = Atorvastatin. Rosu = Rosuvastatin. Simva = Simvastatin. Ezet = Ezetimibe.

4-The Results.

Pre-therapeutic period:

- Long-axis amplitudes and left ventricular (LV) function:** Measurements showed amplitudes ranging from 4.6–13 mm (Types I–IV and VI) and above 13 mm up to 23 mm. As presented in Table (2), **95% of patients (n = 1057)** had normal LV function (EF 65–78%), whereas **5% (n = 56)** exhibited impaired function (EF 25–40%). Patterns of deterioration included:
 - **Type I (56%):** Reduced lateral and septal axes (<11 mm), others normal.
 - **Type II (13%):** Reduced anterior axis (<10 mm).
 - **Type III (11%):** Four axes affected (lateral, septal, anterior, inferior).
 - **Type IV (8%):** Severely reduced lateral axis (6.5 mm) with hyperkinetic anterior (16.8 mm) and inferior (18.7 mm); associated with acute palpitations and dyspnea.
 - **Type V (7%):** Involvement of one LV and one RV axis; patients presented with recurrent dyspnea and predominant back pain.
 - **Type VI (5%):** All axes deteriorated (<7 mm), enlarged LV dimensions, and severe dysfunction (EF ≤25%, FS ≤12%).

Table (2) represents long axes amplitudes of cardiac walls, left ventricular functions and types of axes deterioration according to their presentation

Long axes and left ventricle function	Types* and values of presented long axes amplitudes					
	I (56%)	II (13%)	III (11%)	IV (8%)	V (7%)	VI (5%)
Lateral	10.9	13.8	10.4	06.5	14.7	04.6
Septal	10.9	14.9	09.4	10.3	12.9	06.5
Anterior	11.9	09.8	09.4	16.8	12.9	04.6
Inferior	11.4	13.8	10.9	18.7	13.3	04.6
Posterior	14.4	12.1	12.4	11.5	10.6	05.9
Right Ventricle	20.4	21.2	22.4	23.3	19.3	05.2
LVED	55.2	48.8	40.3	42.8	59.2	70.9
LVES	34.3	30.4	21.9	27.5	34.9	62.4
EF%	67%	68%	78%	65%	71%	25%
FS%	38%	38%	46%	36%	41%	12%

figure 3 presents cardiac views showing different coronary stenoses: beads, string-like stenosis (white arrows), focal hypertrophy-related stenosis (large green arrow), and unilateral wall hypertrophy stenosis (thin green arrow). Atheroma-like projections and complete vessel obliteration are also visible, with light green arrows indicating stenotic areas appearing as black gaps between vessel ends

Figure 4: shows main branch stenosis (large green arrow) and blue collateral segments in between red arteries (white arrows), the photo in right side reveals stenotic one end of this blue collateral vascular segment which means that the inflammatory process involved even the collateral vessels, and also will involve the transplanted one

3- in relation to Tissues threads of gastric and maxillary paranasal sinuses: there are a lot of tissues threads that lead to formation of complex networks or masses as shown in figures (5 &6)

figure 5: gastric threads and mass with Eye – sign (pointing to it by yellow arrow in photo (a), and red arrows and arrows heads in all photos a - d), that considered by me; in previous study, as pathognomonic sign for *H. pylori* diagnosis by ultrasonogram and other radiological methods.

Figure 6: Ultrasonography of the maxillary paranasal sinuses shows tissue threads (green arrows), the radiological pathognomonic “Eye Sign” of *H. pylori* (red arrow), and thread aggregation forming a mass (yellow arrow) in the left image, while the right image depicts the sinus cavity filled with a dense mass of clustered tissue threads.

2) Post-Therapy Findings.

1. Effects of Drugs on Clinical Manifestations, Long-Axis Amplitudes, LV Function, and Coronary Arteries

A. Effects on Clinical Manifestations

- **Symptoms:** Chest, back, and shoulder pain, as well as dyspnea, subsided within 30 minutes in *Group A* following drug intake. No improvement was observed in *Group B* until therapy was initiated, after which their results paralleled *Group A*.
- **Blood Pressure:**
- **Positive effects:** Hypertension decreased by 20/10–30/20 mmHg within 15–30 minutes after two *Clopidogrel* tablets. And A reduction of 20/10 mmHg was achieved after 20–30 minutes of *Atorvastatin* (10 mg), *Simvastatin* (10 mg), *Ginkgo biloba* (80 mg), or *Clarithromycin* (250 mg). Hypotension improved by +10–20/10 mmHg within 30 minutes after *Clopidogrel* (2 tabs) or *Clarithromycin* (250 mg).
- **Negative effects:** A rebound increase of +20/10 mmHg occurred in both hypertensive and hypotensive patients within 30 minutes of single-drug use.

- **Heart Rate and Pulse Volume:** Heart rate declined from 57 → 37 bpm in a 70-year-old female after *Clopidogrel (150 mg)* (negative effect). And A mild decline (61 → 57 bpm) occurred with *Aspirin (75 mg)* (positive effect).
 - *Simvastatin*, *Atorvastatin*, or *Clarithromycin* increased heart rate and pulse volume, rendering weak pulses palpable.
 - Combined regimens sustained improvement, while single-drug use produced temporary effects.
- **Adverse Effects:** Some drugs caused temporary adverse effects—abdominal bloating, headache, hypertension, metabolic disturbances (glucose, lipids, creatinine), joint pain, bradycardia, limb numbness, or impotence—often accompanied by pathological echocardiographic and ultrasonographic changes.

B. Effects on Long-Axis Amplitudes and Left Ventricular (LV) Function:

- **Group A (Treated):** All patients exhibited symptomatic improvement with increased long-axis amplitudes and enhanced LV function (Tables 2 & 3).
- *Type V* showed exceptions—amplitudes and LV function declined after *Clopidogrel (75 mg)* and *Atorvastatin (10 mg)* (ejection fraction 71% → 57%, shortening fraction 41% → 30%)
- Function and amplitudes normalized after *Ginkgo biloba (80 mg)* and half *Rumalaya Forte* tablet, leading to:
 - Restoration of LV function and amplitudes (Tables 2 & 3).
 - Expansion of coronary network extension (Figures 7, 9, 14–16, 19, 24).
 - Elongation and widening of major coronary arteries (Figures 13, 18–21).
- **Group B (Control):** No changes were observed after 30–60 minutes. Improvement occurred only after therapy, matching *Group A* outcomes

Table (3): represents changes in long axes amplitudes of walls of left and right ventricles & left ventricular function after 30 minutes of drugs intake

Long axes and left ventricle function	Improvements after 30 minutes of taking drugs (for cases in table 2)					
	I (56%)	II (13%)	III (11%)	IV (8%)	V (7%)	VI (5%)
Lateral	16.1	12.4	11.9	11.4	15.6	05.7
Septal	10.9	13.4	11.4	13.9	09.8	04.6
Anterior	14.9	14.9	13.4	12.3	13.0	07.5
Inferior	11.5	12.9	12.4	13.9	11.1	05.2
Posterior	14.9	12.4	14.4	12.3	24.1	08.0
Right ventricle	23.5	18.4	19.9	19.6	24.1	08.6
LVED	50.2	50.7	48.2	49.4	62.3	75.7
LVES	30.3	26.0	24.4	31.4	43.3	61.4
EF%	70%	78%	81%	68%	57%	38%
SF%	40%	47%	49%	38%	30%	19%

C) Relation between Long Axes and Coronary Artery Networks Before and After 30 Minutes of Therapy:

In 95% of patients from both groups, drug intake led within 30 minutes to increased long-axis amplitudes and extension of coronary artery networks (Figures 7–12). In 5% of patients, partial improvements were observed, with enhanced amplitudes in some walls and enlarged vascular networks (Figure 12), while other axes showed reduced amplitudes associated with diminished network areas, decreased color flow, and limited collateral formation (Figure 1E–F; Figures 17, 22, 23). Overall, changes in long-axis amplitudes were directly correlated with coronary network expansion and elongation of major arteries.

1) Lateral & Septal long axes amplitudes and coronary arteries networks areas of both walls

Figure 7: Lateral wall axis and coronary arteries—upper images (pre-therapy) show a lateral long-axis amplitude of 10.3 mm with visible coronary vessels, while lower images (post-therapy) reveal a reduced lateral axis amplitude of 8.8 mm. The coronary vessels along the lateral wall appear decreased post-therapy, whereas septal vessels and septal axis amplitude show a noticeable increase.

Figure 8: Septal long axis in upper photo is 6.3 mm as it was measured in pre therapeutic period, and its coronary vessels is shown in the photo beside it, and the lower photos taken in post therapeutic period; the septal long axis is 8.9 mm that mean increased in height by 2.6 mm, and the coronary vessels (red color) in right side become more elongated and wider.

3) Anterior, Inferior, posterior and RV long axes amplitudes and coronary arteries networks areas of these wall:

1) Anterior long axis amplitude and coronary arteries networks areas of anterior wall:

Figure 9: Anterior long axis amplitude in pre therapeutic period is 11.1 mm as shown in left upper photo, and its coronary arteries is shown in right upper photo, while the lower photos are show anterior long axis amplitude height is 12.2 mm in post therapy period after 30 minutes with enlarged extension of coronary arteries as shown in lower right photo.

3) Posterior long axis amplitude and coronary arteries networks areas of posterior wall:

2) Inferior long axis and coronary arteries networks areas of inferior wall:

Figure 10: Long axis of the inferior wall and its coronary vessels—upper images (pre-therapy) show an amplitude of 9.9 mm with visible coronary extension, while lower images (30 minutes post-therapy) reveal an increased amplitude of 11.5 mm and an enlarged coronary vessel area, indicating improved perfusion.

4) Right ventricular long axis amplitude and coronary arteries networks areas of its wall:

Figure 11: Posterior long-axis amplitudes and coronary arteries pre- and 30-minutes post-therapy. In the upper images, the long-axis amplitude is 11.1 mm (left) with coronary artery extension (right) during the pre-therapy period. In the lower images, post-therapy, the posterior long-axis amplitude increases to 14.2 mm, with enlarged coronary vascular extension (colored areas).

Figure 12: Right ventricular long-axis amplitude and coronary vessels pre- and 30 minutes post-therapy. The upper left image shows a 19.5 mm axis with right coronary artery extension pre-therapy. The lower left image shows post-therapy changes, with the axis increased to 20.1 mm and enlargement of the right coronary vascular area, as seen in the lower right image.

D- Effects on coronary arteries areas extension by comparing between their shapes and color extension:

Figure 13: Elongation of coronary artery and visualization of distal beads after 30 minutes of therapy, as seen in right photo, that not visualized in pretherapeutic period as seen in left photo

Figure 14: Dilated cardiomyopathy with reduced ejection fraction. The left (pre-therapy) image shows narrow septal and lateral coronary zones, while the right (post-therapy) image displays enlarged vessels and fine red strands forming a "string-of-beads" pattern near the mitral leaflets between red and blue flows

Figure 15: The left image shows left ventricular coronary arteries with two red zones linked by small vessels and scattered blue areas. The right (post-therapy) image displays well-developed arterial networks, merged blue zones, and renewed left-right coronary connections at ventricular and atrial levels, with an elongated, widened right ventricular red area

Figure 16: A clear contrast is seen between the left and right images. After 30 minutes of drug intake, coronary arteries reappear, with more distinct red and blue arterial networks in the left ventricle and larger red zones with extending vessels in the right ventricle compared to the pre-therapy image.

E- Effects on longer coronary arteries width and length:

Figure 12: left side photo in pre therapeutic period reveals coronary vessels with red and blue colors more than right photo that reveals a reduction in length, width and number of red coronary arteries after drugs intake of ginkgo biloba tab while it return to pre therapeutic period after intake of ginkgo biloba capsule.

Figure 18: Five-chamber view of coronary arteries—left image (pre-therapy) shows short red and blue vessels along the septal wall, while the right image (30 minutes post-therapy) demonstrates increased vessel length and width, disappearance of the distal mosaic segment, and elongation with narrowing of the proximal mosaic segment near the mitral leaflet.

Figure 19: Comparison of pre- and post-therapy images—left image shows a stenosed, shortened right coronary artery, while the right image (30 minutes post-therapy) reveals a longer, wider vessel. The left coronary network (red areas in the atrium and ventricle) displays interrupted gaps pre-therapy that are restored post-therapy through reconnected and newly formed vascular networks.

Figure 20: 5 chambers view, it shows narrowing of branch of left coronary artery in left photo; red color, size 2.1 mm at stenosed site, while it becomes wider; size 5 mm, in right photo after 30 minutes of drugs intake, along with re-emerging of right ventricular CAs multiple short branches, and reducing the hyperechogenic reflection (i.e. reducing fibrosis echogenicity)

F- Effects of drug/drugs on blood flowing in systolic and diastolic phases of Coronary arteries

Figure 21: Diastolic (A, C) and systolic (B, D) phases. Pre-therapy, the posterior descending coronary artery is narrow in diastole (A) and wider in systole (B). After 30 minutes of drug intake, it widens with increased red coronary branches in diastole (C), while in systole (D) the artery becomes thinner and red branches of the posterior descending artery disappear.

G- The negative effects of drugs on coronary arteries

Reduction in CAs numbers and width or calibers as shown in these figures (22, 23 & 24).

Figure 22: Comparison of right and left images shows markedly reduced coronary color areas in the lower LV cavity, with absent vessels in both epicardial and myocardial regions—findings attributed to vasoconstriction induced by Ginkgo biloba tablets, despite their otherwise positive systemic effects at the time.

Figure 23: shows reduction in coronary arteries network areas and collateral vessels in the b & d photos after 30 minutes of Rosuvastatin 10 and 20 mg during its negative period.

Figure 24: Coronary arteries in patients on Aspirin 75 mg and Atorvastatin 20 mg for one month (left image) and vascular changes 30 minutes after two clopidogrel 75 mg tablets (150 mg) intake. During this period, with positive Aspirin effects and transient clopidogrel effects, collateral vessels were reduced in the left image but increased in the right image.

2-Effects of drugs on Maxillary Para-Nasal Sinuses and gastric tissues threads.

A) Gastric Tissues Threads:

1-after 30 minutes of drugs intake there was a reduction in their extension and echogenicity during drugs positive effects as shown in figure (25)

Figure 25: (a) shows gastric tissues threads mass (red arrows) and small area of anechogenic reflection; black color; i.e. water

2-After hours of drugs ingestion, patients felt burning sensation in epigastric; xiphoidal region and expel bloody fluid with masses as seen in figure (26).

Figure 26: Gastric tissue threads — left image shows a single thread (red arrow) with a nodus branching into multiple fibers (blue arrows), forming a

(green arrow) in left photo before drugs intake and reduction in mass of tissues threads (red arrows), with enlarging of black color (water area) as pointing to it by (green arrows) in right photo (b) after 30 minutes of drugs intake.

tissue skeleton vomited 8 hours after sildenafil with pepper, clopidogrel, and atorvastatin. Right image, 4 hours after multiple drugs, shows a large tissue mass (red arrow) covered by jelly-like mucus (green arrow) with smaller branching threads (blue arrows), partially adhering for over three days with extensions visible through the mucus

B)Maxillary Paranasal sinuses Tissues Threads:

Figure27: (a) shows maxillary paranasal sinuse tissues threads with hyperechogenic reflection in left photo before drug intakes and positive effect that leads to reduction in echogenicity (brightness) and increase in black space (green arrow) after 30 minutes of drug intake as seen in right photo (b).

3- Negative Effects Of Drugs on Tissues Threads of Gastric And Maxillary Paranasal Sinuses.

The negative effects of drugs lead to enhancement of echogenicity and stimulation of tissues threads formation, extension and thickening to the degree of mass formation and obliteration of spaces, as shown down

Figure 28: Gastric tissue threads before and 30 minutes after drug intake. The left image shows thickened threads and reduced dark fluid after clopidogrel, indicating tissue extension, while the right image shows thinner threads and an expanded dark area, reflecting rosuvastatin’s negative effect

Figure 29: shows maxillary sinuses with negative effects (increasing of echogenicity and tissues threads extension after 30 minutes of drugs intake; (a) after ginkgo biloba tabs, and (b) after rumalaya forte tab.

Table (4) represent drugs effects on blood pressure, heart rate, pulse volume, tissues threads, Coronary arteries, long axes amplitudes, and left ventricular function

Drugs	Form and dose	Blood Pressure#	HR	Pulse volume*	Tissues Threads				Coronary arteries	Long axes	LV function
					Gastric		Paranasal Sinuses				
					Extensi ons	Echog enicity	Extensi ons	Echoge nicity			
Aspirin	Tab 75 mg	NE	NE	NE	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑
Clopidogrel	Tab 75 mg	NE	NE	NE	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
	Tab 150 mg	↓	↑	NE	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑↑	↑↑	↑↑
Atorvastatin	Tab 10 mg	↓	↑	Improved	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑
Rosuvastatin	Tab 10 mg	↓	NE	NE	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑

Simvastatin	Tab 10 mg	↓	↑	Improved	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑
Clarithromycin	Tab 250 mg	↑	↑	Improved	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑
Ginkgo biloba capsule	Cap 80 mg	↓	↓	NE	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑
Rumalaya forte tabs	Tab	↓	NE	NE	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓

*Pulse volume is improved by using of Clarithromycin, Simvastatin or Atorvastatin.# Blood pressure of hypertensive patients.

5-Discussion.

In a prior study, the full-length examination of coronary arteries using color flow echocardiography revealed several diagnostic patterns of coronary artery disease, including stenosis, tortuosity, and the “strings of beads” sign (Figures 1, 2, 10) [3]. Although this pattern is typically associated with fibromuscular dysplasia in middle-aged females [4, 5], it has also been documented in elderly males with renal atherosclerosis [6]. In earlier work, the researcher found this pattern in both coronary and renal arteries across all age groups [3, 7].

In the current study, the “strings of beads” pattern reappeared in all 1,113 patients (500 females and 613 males) (Figures 1, 2, 3, 13, 14, 20, 24). The study also examined the effects of various drugs and herbal formulations on coronary arteries, long-axis amplitudes (Figures 7–12), and left ventricular dimensions and functions (Tables 2–3). A crucial observation was the delayed coronary flow characterized by an inverted systolic/diastolic ratio (Figure 21), indicating reduced myocardial perfusion.

After therapy, this ratio normalized, and diastolic flow significantly improved—reflecting restored myocardial perfusion [8]. The researcher believes this rapid normalization, accompanied by the reappearance and expansion of coronary arterial networks, highlights the immediate beneficial effects of clopidogrel (150 mg), low-dose statins, ginkgo biloba, and rumalaya forte. Similar vascular responses were previously documented in renal arteries after 30 minutes of drug intake [9]. These results, in the researcher’s view, confirm that the drugs relieve transient vasoconstriction and stenosis, enhancing perfusion and cardiac contractility.

The further questions how such rapid physiological improvements occur before drug metabolism. He posits that these effects arise from the **stimulation of cytokine release** upon the initial contact of drug particles with the gastric mucosa. This hypothesis is supported by clinical evidence showing a sharp blood pressure drop (20/10–60/40 mmHg) and chest pain relief within 15 minutes—well before the hepatic activation of clopidogrel [10, 11]. Therefore, the researcher believes clopidogrel and low-dose statins may trigger vasodilatory and cardiotoxic effects indirectly through **gastric-induced cytokine signaling**.

Cytokines—proteins that interact with specific cell receptors—regulate immune responses and cellular functions via autocrine, paracrine, and endocrine pathways [12, 13]. Accordingly, the researcher concludes that the **anti-inflammatory, immunomodulatory, antioxidant, and anti-fibrotic** effects of clopidogrel, statins, ginkgo biloba, rumalaya forte, and clarithromycin are mediated through the up- or down-regulation of cytokine pathways, as summarized in Table 5

Table (5): represents cytokines and effects on them by drugs and H. pylori

Cytokines	Clopidogrel	Atorva- statin	Rosuva- statin	Simva- statin	Ginkgo biloba	Rumalaya Forte	Aspirin	H.pylori
IL-1 alpha	Dec[14]		Inc [33]			DR[43]		Act[53, 54]
IL-1 beta	Dec [19,29]	Inc [30]	Dec[30]		Dec[39, 41]	DR[43]	Inc[49, 62]	Act[53, 54]
IL-2	Dec[14]		Inc [33]			DR[43] Enh[44]		Act[54]

						(glycyrrhizin)		
IL-4			Inc[16]	Inc [35, 37]		UR[43]	NE[50]	
IL-5				Inc[35, 37]				
IL-6	Dec[14, 29]		Dec[16]		Inh[41]	DR[43, 48]	Inc[49] Dec[50]	Act[53, 54]
IL-8	Dec[15]		Inc[16]		Inh[40]	DR[44]		Act[53]
IL-10	Dec[14,29]	Inc [30, 31]	Dec[33]	Inc[38]	UR[39]	UR[43] Dec[48]	Inc[49] NE[50]	Act[53, 54]
IL-12						Enh[44]		Act[53, 54]
IL-13	Dec[14]			Inc[33, 37]				Act[54]
IL-17	Dec [19]	Dec [31]			DR[43]	Dec[45]		Act[53, 54]
IL-18		Dec[30]						Act[53, 54]
IL-21		Dec [30]						
IL-23		Dec [30]		Dec[37]				Act[53, 54]
IL-35		Dec [30]	Dec[30]					
IL-37		Inc [30]	Inc[30]					
IFN-gamma	Inc[29]	Dec [31]	NE [16]	Dec[35, 37]	Inh [63]	DR[43] Enh[44]	Red [62]	Act[53]
TNF-alpha	Dec[15]		Inc [16]		Dec[40, 41]	DR[43, 48]	Dec [50, 51]	Act[53]
TNF- beta	Dec[14]							
TGF-beta	Dec[16] Red[23]	Inc [30]	Dec[30]	Inc[35]	Inh [63]	ND	Inh[52,64] Inc [65]	Act[53]
P-selectin	Prev[16]							
ICAM-1	Red [17] [23]					Dec[46]		Act [96]
VCAM-1	Red [17]					Dec[46]		Act [96]
ERK	Supp.[17]							Act[56]
JNK	Supp[17]					UR[47]		Act[56]
ROS	Red[17]				Dec[41]		Dec [50]	
Nrf2	Act[17] UR [23, 84]	Act [66]	Act [67]	Act [68]	Ac[69]	ND	Act [70] Atten[71]	Inh [72]
NF-kB	Prev [18, 23]	Red [73]	Inh[74, 76]	Supp [75]	DR[42, 78]	Dec[48]	Mod[51] Inh[64]	Act.[56]
Ang II	Supp [18]				Inh[63]			
P2Y12	Inh[16]						NE [16]	
TLR2				Dec[60]				Act.[56,57]
TLR4	Act [78] Inh [16]	Supp [63]	Inh [79]	Dec[60]	Inh [77]	ND	NE[58] Inh[64]	Act.[54, 56]
Treg	Dec[28]	Reg [31]		Inc[35]	UR[43]			Induce[53]
VEGF	NE [20] Dec [22]		Inc[16]		Inh[40]	Dec[47]	Inc[52]	
VEGF-VEGFR2-ERK Signaling	Inh [11]							
PDGF-AB	NE [21] Dec[22]						Inc[52]	
MCP-1	Dec[23]	Dec[73]	Inc[16]					
SOCS3	ND			Inc[37]				
SOCS7	ND							
Foxp3	ND			Inc[35, 37]	Inc[43]	Dec[45]		Inc[53]
SMAD6	ND			Dec[35, 37]				
SMAD7	ND			Dec[35, 37]				

Diff. CD40	ND			Inc[35]				
Diff. Th17	ND			Dec[38]		PREV[45]		
GATA3	ND			Inc[36]				
JAK/STAT	ND			Dec[37]		PREV[45]		
STAT/NF-kB	Supp [23]							Act[56]
NLRP1	Inh[24]						Inh[24]	
NLRP3	Supp [23, 17]	Supp [59]	Inh [76]	Inh [79]	Inh [81]	ND	Inh [82]	Act [80]
TGF-b1/Smad3/ P2RY12 pathway	Blocked [17]							
TGF-b1/Smad2/ EMT pathway								Act[93]
Cox-1	NE[25]						Inh[52]	
Cox-2	NE[25]				DR[42]	Dec[47]	Inh[52]	
MMP9	ND					Dec [47]		
MAPK	Supp [26]				Mod[41]	Prev[48]		Act[56]
AMPK	Red [23] Act [84]				Mod[41]			
prostaglandin	NE[27]					Dec[43, 48]		
Eotaxin-1	ND					DR[43]		
iNOS	Inh[19]				Supp[61]		Dec[51]	
PPAR gamma	Reg [86]	Act [86]	Act [87]	Act [85]	Reg [83]	ND	Act [88]	DR[55]
ET-1	Inh*							
Fibronectin	Red [23]							
RANTES (ccl-5)	Supp [23]							
Th1/Th17		Dec [32]						
Th1		Dec [32]						
Th2		Inc [32]						
MMT		Inh [16]						
Leukotrienes						Dec[43]		
GM-CSF								Act[54]

Dec= decrease. Inc= increase. Reg = regulate. UR. = upregulate. DR. = down regulate. Prev. = prevention. Act. = activated. Supp = suppressive.

Inh. = inhibition. MMT = Macrophage to Myofibroblast transition. Atten =Attenuates. Mod = modulate

H. Pylori and the TLR4-Mediated Inflammatory Response:

Many pro-atherogenic cytokines such as IL-1, TNF- α , and IFN- γ contribute to lipid metabolism disorders and chronic inflammation [89, 90]. This inflammatory state, largely mediated by TLR4 activation [92], plays a critical role in aging-related diseases [91]. TLR4, an innate immune receptor, responds to bacterial lipopolysaccharide (LPS) and endogenous ligands produced during inflammation [94, 95].

Gastric *H. pylori* infection exemplifies this mechanism. The bacteria induce structural changes in the gastric mucosa [96], forming long, branching “threads” (Figures 5, 6, 26) where bacteria persist. These structures may continuously stimulate TLR4, maintaining chronic inflammation even after antibiotic therapy. *H. pylori* thus manipulates immune regulation by altering cytokine expression and activating key pathways including TLR4, TGF- β , NF-KB, and MAPK [54, 56, 93]. The researcher interprets these findings as evidence of persistent immune stimulation that sustains systemic inflammation.

Systemic TLR4 Activation and Disease:

The pro-inflammatory influence of *H. pylori* extends beyond the stomach, activating both TLR2 and TLR4 in epithelial tissues [54, 56, 58]. TLR4 upregulation has been documented in distant organs, such as atherosclerotic plaques [97], the aging brain [99], and cardiac and aortic tissues [91]. Furthermore, TLR4 agonists can trigger endothelin-1 release, leading to vasoconstriction [98]. The improvement in brain function and histology after administering tea polyphenols—a known TLR4

inhibitor—via nasogastric tube [99] underscores TLR4's central role in systemic inflammation and neurovascular health. The researcher believes this provides a mechanistic link between gastrointestinal inflammation and multisystem disease progression.

H. pylori's Impact on Immune Homeostasis:

H. pylori disrupts immune homeostasis by activating pro-inflammatory mediators (IL-1 β , IL-2, IL-6, TNF- α) and signaling cascades (TLR2/4, NF-KB, NLRP3 inflammasome) [54, 56, 57, 80], while suppressing antioxidant and regulatory pathways such as Nrf2 and PPAR- γ [72, 55]. This imbalance promotes chronic inflammation that extends to various organs, impairing both histological and physiological functions. However, the reversal of TLR4-driven pathology—such as restored memory and hippocampal integrity after inhibition [99]—suggests that these inflammatory disorders may be reversible under targeted modulation.

Reversal of Pathological Changes and the Post-Pandemic Paradox:

Certain drugs, herbs, and foods may counteract the inflammatory sequelae of *H. pylori* and SARS-CoV-2 through TLR pathway modulation. Clarithromycin, for instance, inhibits gastric TLR4 expression and downregulates pro-inflammatory cytokines (IL-12, IL-18) induced by *H. pylori* [101, 102]. Clinically, this translates into improved cardiac function, normalized blood pressure in both hypertensive and hypotensive patients, and enhanced peripheral circulation. Moreover, clarithromycin regulates intestinal motility and aids in shedding abnormal gastric and paranasal sinus tissue threads (Figure 26) by reducing inflammatory cytokines and growth factors, downregulating LPS-induced TLR4, and upregulating CTLA-4—an essential immune checkpoint protein [100–102]. The researcher views these effects as evidence of a systemic anti-inflammatory mechanism capable of reversing chronic pathological processes

Drug Effects and the Post-COVID-19 Era:

Low-dose clopidogrel previously showed minimal effect on inflammatory protein upregulation in diabetic mice [19]; however, our study demonstrates that a higher dose (150 mg) is necessary to reduce inflammation, induce vasodilation, lower blood pressure, enhance cardiac contractility, and inhibit fibrosis. The researcher believes these effects occur primarily at the gastric level, modulating key “controller points” within TLR pathways.

The TLR4 pathway, implicated in persistent inflammation and aging-related disorders [91], can be inhibited by clopidogrel [17]. This reduces pro-inflammatory cytokines such as IL-1 α and IL-1 β [14, 19, 29], thereby decreasing vasoconstrictive agents like endothelin-1. Clinically, this manifested as reduced effort-induced fatigue and improved coronary visibility within 30 minutes of drug intake (Figures 2C, E, F, 14–16, 21).

Conflicting evidence exists on clopidogrel's action on TLR4: some studies report inhibition [17], others activation [78], especially post-COVID-19. Unpublished data indicate that low-dose clopidogrel's benefits diminished post-pandemic, with paradoxical increases in blood pressure at 150 mg (mid-2025). Similarly, Simvastatin shifted from activating to reducing IFN- γ , and Aspirin's effect on TGF- β changed from activating to suppressive [34, 36, 64, 65]. These observations highlight that SARS-CoV-2 variants fundamentally alter inflammatory pathways and drug responses, necessitating a review of therapeutic strategies in the post-pandemic era.

A Shared Inflammatory Pathway:

H. pylori and SARS-CoV-2 trigger similar pro-inflammatory cascades, including TGF- β , NF-KB, TLR4, MAPK, and NLRP3 [54–56, 80, 103–105], while inhibiting regulatory pathways such as PPAR- γ and Nrf2 [55, 61, 106, 107]. The researcher interprets this shared profile as a common inflammatory mechanism that the discussed drugs effectively target. Their consistent

ability to reverse pathology indicates action on a fundamental inflammatory process, whether chronic (*H. pylori*) or acute-on-chronic (SARS-CoV-2).

Links to Atherosclerosis and Fibromuscular Dysplasia:

Inflammatory markers activated by *H. pylori* and SARS-CoV-2 are also characteristic of atherosclerosis (AS) and fibromuscular dysplasia (FMD) [93, 108, 109]. The similarity, including ICAM-1 and VCAM-1 activation [108–110], suggests *H. pylori* may contribute to or trigger FMD and AS. The researcher proposes advanced imaging or histological examination to identify the “EYE-SIGN” in affected tissues—a known indicator of *H. pylori*-induced inflammation.

Pathogenic Synergy and Therapeutic Implications:

Several researchers have proposed *H. pylori* as a pathogenic cofactor in multiple diseases, including COVID-19 [2]. The coexistence of SARS-CoV-2 and chronic *H. pylori* infection appears to intensify inflammation, forming dense, “ball-like” masses in gastric tissues. Since both pathogens are linked to cardiovascular disease, viral infection can exacerbate atherosclerosis (AS) and fibromuscular dysplasia (FMD). The researcher believes that therapeutic strategies modulating shared inflammatory pathways—such as those described previously [9]—may reverse this complex, multi-system pathology.

Evolving Treatment Strategies in the Post-Pandemic Era:

Drug efficacy and administration routes must be continuously adjusted due to persistent and sequential changes in SARS-CoV-2 variants. Between 2022 and early 2025, 150 mg clopidogrel with a statin sufficed. From April–July 2025, effective anticoagulants shifted to aspirin and Ginkgo biloba. By late July, two-drug regimens became insufficient, necessitating multi-drug therapies, with substitutions including clarithromycin, amoxicillin, cefixim, cefadroxil, and *Embllica officinalis* by late August 2025. The researcher interprets these shifts as evidence of the virus dynamically altering inflammatory responses, requiring adaptive treatment strategies.

The Cytokine-Mediated Mechanism:

These dynamic adjustments are necessary because emerging viral variants activate distinct cytokine profiles. Drugs with synergistic pro-inflammatory effects may worsen outcomes. For example:

- Variants activating IL-1 α : rosuvastatin or simvastatin may exacerbate symptoms.
- Variants activating IL-1 β : atorvastatin may worsen the patient’s condition.
- Variants activating IFN- γ : clopidogrel or simvastatin alone may be detrimental.

The researcher emphasizes that drug choice and combinations must be tailored to counteract variant-specific inflammatory pathways, with additional agents used to inhibit harmful cytokines and ensure clinical improvement.

Therapeutic Regulation of the Immune Response:

Targeting TLR4 alone is inadequate due to complex cytokine interactions; even IL-10 can trigger JAK/STAT pathways, affecting pro-inflammatory genes [89]. Cytokines like IL-2 and IL-10 may unintentionally aid pathogens such as *H. pylori* and SARS-CoV-2 [111]. Therefore, complete TLR4 inhibition is suboptimal; targeted regulation of TLR signaling, achievable with drugs like clarithromycin, is required. The researcher emphasizes that therapeutic regimens must adapt continuously to circulating SARS-CoV-2 variants and new *H. pylori* exposures to ensure efficacy and prevent paradoxical effects.

Key Findings and Clinical Implications:

- **Diagnostic and Imaging Methods**
 - Color flow and transthoracic echocardiography provide effective, non-invasive approaches for early diagnosis and follow-up of coronary artery disease and myocardial perfusion abnormalities.

- Doppler ultrasonography reliably identifies vascular signs of both atherosclerosis (AS) and fibromuscular dysplasia (FMD) in the same patients.
- Gastric and paranasal sinus ultrasound offers a simple method to monitor the effectiveness of drug therapies by observing tissue threads and wall changes.
- **Drug Efficacy and Pathology**
 - High-dose clopidogrel (150 mg) with an appropriate statin significantly regulates blood pressure, enhances cardiac contractility, and reduces coronary stenosis by 20–30% within 15–30 minutes.
 - Clarithromycin modulates cardiac, vascular, and blood pressure functions while facilitating the reduction and clearance of H. pylori–induced tissue threads.
 - Improvements in fibrosis, seen as decreased hyperechogenicity on echocardiograms, can serve as rapid indicators of therapeutic success.
- **Pathogenesis and Therapeutic Direction**
 - H. pylori is a primary contributor to vascular diseases (AS, FMD), with SARS-CoV-2 amplifying inflammation.
 - Shared cytokine profiles indicate a common inflammatory mechanism, amenable to targeted therapy.
 - Effective drugs function as “controller point regulators,” modulating CTLA-4 and TLR4 to reverse tissue pathology.
 - Coronary network decline and collateral vessel stenosis highlight the need to control underlying inflammation to prevent re-stenosis and organ injury

Recommendations.

1. Adopt non-invasive, cost-effective diagnostics (cardiac/abdominal ultrasound) for faster detection and improved patient outcomes.
2. Personalize therapeutic regimens based on circulating SARS-CoV-2 variants to avoid paradoxical drug effects.
3. Include comprehensive H. pylori screening and treatment in cardiovascular disease guidelines.
4. Develop drugs targeting key inflammatory pathways (e.g., TLR4, CTLA-4) rather than just alleviating symptoms.
5. Implement long-term pharmacovigilance for adverse or paradoxical drug effects, especially with emerging pathogens.
6. Educate clinicians on variable drug and herb effects depending on patients’ inflammatory states.
7. **Further Research:**
 - Histological and imaging studies to confirm H. pylori–induced markers in AS and FMD tissues.
 - Comparative analyses of cytokines, growth factors, and receptors in AS, FMD, H. pylori, and SARS-CoV-2 to validate mechanistic links.
 - Controlled studies to determine how SARS-CoV-2 variants alter therapeutic efficacy of drugs like clopidogrel and statins.

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